

Effect Of 5% EMLA Cream Application on Tracheal Tube Cuff on Post-Operative Sore Throat in Adult Female Patients Undergoing Gynaecological Surgery. A Randomized Prospective Controlled Study

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ABSTRACT

Postoperative sore throat (POST), cough, and hoarseness are common after endotracheal intubation, affecting up to 70% of patients and reducing satisfaction. Evidence for topical EMLA cream in preventing these complications is limited. This study assessed the efficacy of 5% EMLA cream applied to the endotracheal tube (ETT) cuff in female patients undergoing gynaecological surgery. **Materials and Methods:** In this randomized, double-blinded trial at MGMCH, Jaipur (March 2023–August 2024), 220 ASA I–II women (20–60 years) undergoing elective gynaecological surgery under general anaesthesia were enrolled. Group A (n=110) received 2.5 mL of 5% EMLA cream on the ETT cuff; Group B (n=110) received KY Jelly. POST, cough, and hoarseness were scored (0–3 scale) at 0, 2, 4, 6, 12, and 24 hours post-extubation. Data were analysed using chi-square and Student's t-test. **Results:** The EMLA group had significantly less POST at 0–12 hours ($p < 0.01$), with differences disappearing by 24 hours. Early cough and hoarseness were also reduced ($p < 0.05$). Fewer EMLA patients required treatment for POST. No adverse effects were noted. **Conclusion:** Topical 5% EMLA cream on the ETT cuff is a safe, simple method that effectively reduces POST, cough, and hoarseness in the early postoperative period, improving patient comfort.

Keywords: Postoperative sore throat, EMLA cream, Endotracheal tube, Hoarseness, Cough

INTRODUCTION

Postoperative sore throat (POST) is one of the most common complications following tracheal intubation under general anaesthesia, with an incidence ranging from 20% to 70% in adult patients and a particularly high prevalence among those undergoing gynaecological surgery¹. Although generally self-limiting, POST negatively impacts patient satisfaction and may delay postoperative recovery, making its prevention clinically relevant. The endotracheal tube (ETT), introduced in the early 1900s, is typically composed of polyvinyl chloride or silicone and is widely used to maintain airway patency and facilitate mechanical ventilation^{2,3}. Even when inserted correctly by skilled anaesthesiologists, intubation can cause complications, as short-term use of ETTs may result in mucosal trauma from pressure or friction,

leading to sore throat, hoarseness, cough, or even vocal cord injury^{4,5}. Furthermore, incomplete sealing of the airway by the tube cuff predisposes patients to aspiration, thereby increasing the risk of respiratory complications⁶.

The precise pathophysiological mechanism of POST remains incompletely understood, but it is thought to arise from mucosal injury of the laryngeal and tracheal epithelium during intubation, resulting in local inflammation and nociceptive pain⁷. Studies suggest that supraglottic injury may be caused by laryngoscope insertion, while subglottic trauma is more likely attributable to contact with the ETT⁸. This tissue damage triggers the release of inflammatory mediators, leading to oedema and sore throat symptoms. Recent investigations also indicate that mitochondrial DNA released into the upper

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airway acts as a damage-associated molecular pattern (DAMP), activating immune cells and stimulating pro-inflammatory cytokine secretion. These mediators activate the TRPV1 nociceptive receptor, contributing to neuropathic pain responses⁹. Hoarseness of voice is another frequently reported airway complication, affecting nearly half of patients immediately after extubation. While usually transient, some patients may experience prolonged symptoms due to persistent irritation of the vocal cords^{10,11}. In addition, extubation often provokes cough of varying intensity, largely due to irritation from the inflated cuff exerting pressure on laryngeal structures¹².

To minimise the incidence of POST and related airway symptoms, both pharmacological and non-pharmacological strategies are employed. Pharmacological measures include corticosteroids, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, topical anaesthetics, and NMDA receptor antagonists, all of which aim to reduce mucosal inflammation and nociceptive signalling. Non-pharmacological methods, such as the use of video-assisted laryngoscopy, help decrease insertional trauma by improving visibility and reducing force during intubation. In the present study, EMLA cream was investigated as a topical anaesthetic to reduce POST, hoarseness, and cough. EMLA is a eutectic mixture of local anaesthetics containing lidocaine (2.5%) and prilocaine (2.5%), formulated to enhance absorption and provide effective local anaesthesia. By blocking sodium ion influx into nerve fibres, it prevents the initiation and propagation of pain signals, thereby potentially reducing airway irritation associated with intubation. Application of EMLA cream to the ETT cuff offers a targeted approach to limit mucosal injury and subsequent inflammation.

Despite the frequent occurrence of extubation-related symptoms, there is a paucity of research evaluating the efficacy of topical anaesthetic application for their prevention. Such complications can hinder recovery and delay resumption of basic functions, such as swallowing, speaking, and eating, thereby reducing overall patient satisfaction^{13,14}. This study was therefore designed to address this gap. Patients were randomly divided into two groups: one receiving 5% EMLA cream applied to the ETT cuff, and the other (control group) receiving KY jelly, a lubricant

commonly used to reduce friction but lacking anaesthetic properties. The severity of symptoms was assessed using a four-point scale, where 0 represented no symptoms, 1 mild, 2 moderate, and 3 severe.

The aim of this study is to assess the efficacy of EMLA 5% cream in reducing the incidence and severity of postoperative sore throat, hoarseness, and cough. Secondary objectives include evaluating the number of patients requiring additional treatment for POST and identifying any adverse effects such as allergic reactions or mucosal injury evidenced by blood on the ETT. Through this investigation, we aim to enhance postoperative care, improve recovery, and increase patient satisfaction by providing a simple and effective method to reduce airway-related complications.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design: This study was designed as a prospective, randomized, double-blind, hospital-based trial conducted in the Department of Anaesthesia at MGMCH, Jaipur. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee prior to commencement, and written informed consent was taken from all participants. The study was carried out between March 2023 and August 2024, in accordance with ethical standards for clinical research.

Study Setting and Study Place: The trial was conducted in the operating theatres of MGMCH, Jaipur, involving adult female patients undergoing elective gynaecological surgeries under general anaesthesia. All eligible patients were assessed during the preoperative 45-minute evaluation, where they were informed about the study protocol, assessment tools, and symptom scoring systems for evaluating postoperative sore throat (POST), cough, and hoarseness of voice.

Methodology: A total of 220 patients were enrolled and randomized into two groups of 110 each. Randomization was performed using computer-generated sequences, with allocation concealed to ensure double blinding of both patients and investigators. Group A received 2.5 mL of 5% EMLA cream applied to the cuff and distal portion of the endotracheal tube, while Group B received 2.5 mL of

a water-based lubricant gel (KY Jelly) applied in the same manner.

All patients were premedicated with intravenous midazolam (0.03–0.05 mg/kg), ondansetron (0.1 mg/kg), and fentanyl (2 µg/kg). Anaesthesia was induced using intravenous propofol, titrated to the loss of verbal response, followed by vecuronium bromide (0.1 mg/kg) to facilitate tracheal intubation. Intubation was performed using a single-use endotracheal tube of internal diameter 6.0 or 6.5 mm, equipped with a high-volume, low-pressure cuff.

Cuff pressure was monitored hourly throughout surgery and maintained within recommended limits. Anaesthesia was maintained with isoflurane in a 1:1 oxygen-to-air mixture. At the conclusion of surgery, neuromuscular blockade was reversed with intravenous glycopyrrolate (0.01 mg/kg) and neostigmine (0.05 mg/kg). Postoperative analgesia included intravenous paracetamol (15 mg/kg), administered intraoperatively and continued every six hours for 24 hours. Patients were observed for the incidence and severity of POST, hoarseness, and cough, which were scored using a 4-point scale: 0 = no symptoms, 1 = mild symptoms, 2 = moderate symptoms, 3 = severe symptoms

Sample Size and Study Population: The sample size was determined using the method of comparing two independent means, with the anticipated standard deviation of POST at 11%. The final sample size was

calculated as 220 patients (110 in each group), ensuring a 5% level of significance and 90% study power. Parameters used in calculation included an absolute error (E) of 5.5%, Z_{α} of 1.96 at 95% confidence, and $Z_{1-\beta}$ of 0.8413 at 80% power.

Inclusion criteria were female patients aged 20–60 years, ASA grade I and II, scheduled for elective gynaecological surgeries under general anaesthesia, and who provided informed consent.

Exclusion criteria included patients with a history of smoking, cough, drug allergies, difficult airway, more than two intubation attempts, or pre-existing sore throat.

Statistical Analysis: All collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel for statistical processing. Categorical variables were expressed as frequency and percentage, while continuous variables were summarized as mean with standard error of mean (SEM). Normality of continuous data was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Comparisons between groups were carried out using Student's t-test for continuous variables and Chi-square or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. The Chi-square test was used to examine associations between categorical variables, with degrees of freedom calculated as $n-1$. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Results:

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of patients in the two study groups

Parameter	Categories	EMLA (n=110)	KY Jelly (n=110)	Statistical test	p-value
Age (years)	18–30	38	47	Student's t-test	0.2136
	31–45	40	38		0.1237
	46–60	32	25		0.1038
ASA Grade	I	75 (68.18%)	81 (73.64%)	Chi-square	—
	II	35 (31.82%)	29 (26.36%)		—
	III	1 (0.91%)	0		—
Duration of Surgery	≤ 1 hour	21	35	Chi-square	0.06
	1–2 hours	52	49		0.38
	2–3 hours	26	19		1.089
	>3 hours	11	7		0.34

Values expressed as numbers (n) or percentages (%).

ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists.

Statistical analysis performed using Student's t-test for continuous variables and Chi-square test for categorical variables.

Discussion of Baseline Characteristics: The distribution of baseline characteristics across both study groups demonstrates that the EMLA and KY Jelly cohorts were well matched, minimizing the likelihood of confounding effects.

With respect to age, the majority of patients in both groups were in the younger age categories (18–30 and 31–45 years). The distribution was comparable, with no statistically significant differences observed ($p > 0.05$ across all age groups). This balance reduces the possibility of age-related bias in outcomes such as tissue healing, perception of pain, or airway reactivity.

When assessed by ASA grade, most patients were classified as Grade I, indicating good preoperative health status. A smaller proportion were Grade II,

while only one patient in the EMLA group was classified as Grade III. The near-identical distribution of ASA grades between the two groups confirms that the overall systemic health of patients was comparable, ensuring internal validity when comparing postoperative complications.

Analysis of surgical duration revealed no statistically significant differences between the groups ($p > 0.05$). Most procedures in both cohorts lasted between one and two hours, with smaller subsets of patients undergoing shorter or longer operations. Since surgical duration is a known factor that can influence postoperative sore throat and airway morbidity, the comparable distribution between groups strengthens the reliability of outcome comparisons.

Overall, the demographic and clinical characteristics at baseline were homogenous between the two study groups. This balanced distribution supports the conclusion that any differences in postoperative sore throat, hoarseness, or cough observed in later analyses are attributable to the intervention (EMLA cream application) rather than to patient or surgical variability.

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to POST severity scores at different time points

Time (hrs)	Severity	EMLA (n=110)	KY Jelly (n=110)	χ^2 value	p-value
0 hr	No POST	59	17	23.21	<0.01**
	Mild	20	43	10.88	0.003**
	Moderate	26	46	5.55	0.018*
	Severe	5	4	0.12	0.72
2 hr	No POST	51	12	24.12	<0.01**
	Mild	29	88	29.75	0.001**
	Moderate	30	6	16	0.001**
	Severe	0	4	4	0.045*
4 hr	No POST	96	54	11.76	0.0006**
	Mild	7	54	36.21	<0.01**
	Moderate	7	2	2.78	0.09
	Severe	0	0	0	–
6 hr	No POST	95	68	2.78	0.09
	Mild	10	27	7.81	0.005**
	Moderate	5	15	5	0.025*
	Severe	0	0	0	–

12 hr	No POST	105	92	0.86	0.35
	Mild	5	18	7.34	0.006**
	Moderate	0	0	0	–
	Severe	0	0	0	–
24 hr	No POST	107	103	0.077	0.78
	Mild	3	7	1.6	0.20
	Moderate	0	0	0	–
	Severe	0	0	0	–

Values expressed as number of patients.

POST = Postoperative sore throat.

Severity scale: 0 = None, 1 = Mild, 2 = Moderate, 3 = Severe. Statistical analysis performed using Chi-square test. $p < 0.05$ = significant (*), $p < 0.01$ = highly significant (**).

Table 2 summarizes the severity of postoperative sore throat (POST) at different time intervals in both groups. At 0 hours, significantly more patients in the EMLA group reported no POST (59 vs 17; $\chi^2=23.21$, $p<0.01$ **), while fewer experienced mild (20 vs 43; $\chi^2=10.88$, $p=0.003$ ***) and moderate symptoms (26 vs 46; $\chi^2=5.55$, $p=0.018$ *); severe POST was rare and comparable (5 vs 4; $\chi^2=0.12$, $p=0.72$). At 2 hours, the EMLA group again showed more patients without POST (51 vs 12; $\chi^2=24.12$, $p<0.01$ ***) and fewer with mild symptoms (29 vs 88; $\chi^2=29.75$, $p=0.001$ **), although moderate cases were paradoxically higher

(30 vs 6; $\chi^2=16$, $p=0.001$ **); severe POST occurred only in the KY Jelly group (0 vs 4; $\chi^2=4$, $p=0.045$ *). At 4 hours, 96 patients in the EMLA group were symptom-free compared to 54 in the KY Jelly group ($\chi^2=11.76$, $p=0.0006$ **), with mild symptoms remaining significantly fewer in the EMLA cohort (7 vs 54; $\chi^2=36.21$, $p<0.01$ **); moderate cases showed no significant difference (7 vs 2; $\chi^2=2.78$, $p=0.09$), and no severe POST was observed in either group. At 6 hours, symptom-free patients were more in the EMLA group (95 vs 68; $\chi^2=2.78$, $p=0.09$), while mild (10 vs 27; $\chi^2=7.81$, $p=0.005$ ***) and moderate (5 vs 15; $\chi^2=5$, $p=0.025$ *) symptoms were significantly fewer. By 12 hours, most patients were asymptomatic (105 vs 92; $\chi^2=0.86$, $p=0.35$), with only mild symptoms remaining significantly lower in the EMLA group (5 vs 18; $\chi^2=7.34$, $p=0.006$ **). At 24 hours, both groups showed near-complete resolution (107 vs 103; $\chi^2=0.077$, $p=0.78$), with only a few mild cases (3 vs 7; $\chi^2=1.6$, $p=0.20$), and no moderate or severe cases in either group.

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to Cough severity scores at different time points

Time (hrs)	Severity	EMLA (n=110)	KY Jelly (n=110)	χ^2 value	p-value
0 hr	No Cough	76	28	22.15	0.0001**
	Mild	19	50	34.5	0.0001**
	Moderate	15	32	23.5	0.0001**
	Severe	0	0	0	–
2 hr	No Cough	92	54	9.89	0.0017**
	Mild	11	55	29.33	0.0001**
	Moderate	7	1	4.5	0.03*
	Severe	0	0	0	–
4 hr	No Cough	103	55	14.58	0.0001**
	Mild	6	40	25.13	0.0001**
	Moderate	1	15	12.25	0.0001**
	Severe	0	0	0	–
6 hr	No Cough	105	71	6.56	0.01*
	Mild	5	33	20.63	0.001**

	Moderate	0	6	6	0.014*
	Severe	0	0	0	–
12 hr	No Cough	98	91	0.12	0.72
	Mild	8	13	1.19	0.28
	Moderate	4	6	0.4	0.52
	Severe	0	0	0	–
24 hr	No Cough	98	90	0.34	0.56
	Mild	7	9	0.25	0.61
	Moderate	5	11	2.25	0.73
	Severe	0	0	0	–

Values expressed as number of patients. Severity scale: 0 = None, 1 = Mild, 2 = Moderate, 3 = Severe. Statistical analysis performed using Chi-square test. $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant (*), $p < 0.01$ = highly significant (**).

Table 3 presents the distribution of cough severity at different postoperative intervals. At 0 hours, a significantly greater number of patients in the EMLA group had no cough (76 vs 28; $\chi^2=22.15$, $p=0.0001^{**}$), while mild (19 vs 50; $\chi^2=34.5$, $p=0.0001^{**}$) and moderate cough (15 vs 32; $\chi^2=23.5$, $p=0.0001^{**}$) were more prevalent in the KY Jelly group; no severe cough occurred. At 2 hours, cough-free patients were again higher in the EMLA group (92 vs 54; $\chi^2=9.89$, $p=0.0017^{**}$), with fewer mild cases (11 vs 55; $\chi^2=29.33$, $p=0.0001^{**}$) and more moderate cases (7 vs 1; $\chi^2=4.5$, $p=0.03^*$). At 4 hours,

most patients in the EMLA group had no cough (103 vs 55; $\chi^2=14.58$, $p=0.0001^{**}$), while mild (6 vs 40; $\chi^2=25.13$, $p=0.0001^{**}$) and moderate cough (1 vs 15; $\chi^2=12.25$, $p=0.0001^{**}$) remained significantly more common in the KY Jelly cohort. At 6 hours, the EMLA group again had a higher cough-free rate (105 vs 71; $\chi^2=6.56$, $p=0.01^*$), with significantly fewer mild (5 vs 33; $\chi^2=20.63$, $p=0.001^{**}$) and moderate cases (0 vs 6; $\chi^2=6$, $p=0.014^*$). At 12 hours, differences diminished, with similar cough-free patients (98 vs 91; $\chi^2=0.12$, $p=0.72$) and no significant variation in mild (8 vs 13; $\chi^2=1.19$, $p=0.28$) or moderate cough (4 vs 6; $\chi^2=0.4$, $p=0.52$). By 24 hours, both groups showed stabilization, with no significant difference in cough-free rates (98 vs 90; $\chi^2=0.34$, $p=0.56$) or in mild (7 vs 9; $\chi^2=0.25$, $p=0.61$) and moderate cough (5 vs 11; $\chi^2=2.25$, $p=0.73$), while severe cough remained absent throughout.

Table 4: Distribution of patients according to Hoarseness severity scores at different time points

Time (hrs)	Severity	EMLA (n=110)	KY Jelly (n=110)	χ^2 value	p-value
0 hr	No Hoarseness	76	36	14.28	0.0002**
	Mild	21	60	18.78	0.0001**
	Moderate	13	9	0.72	0.40
	Severe	0	5	5	0.025*
2 hr	No Hoarseness	97	71	4.02	0.04*
	Mild	9	27	9	0.002**
	Moderate	4	12	4	0.045*
	Severe	0	0	0	–
4 hr	No Hoarseness	107	89	1.65	NS
	Mild	3	21	13.5	0.002*
	Moderate	0	0	0	–
	Severe	0	0	0	–
6 hr	No Hoarseness	109	103	0.17	0.68
	Mild	1	7	4.5	0.035*
12 hr	No Hoarseness	110	107	0.04	0.84
	Mild	0	3	3	0.08
24 hr	No Hoarseness	110	109	0.0004	0.98
	Mild	0	1	1	0.31

Values expressed as number of patients. Severity scale: 0 = None, 1 = Mild, 2 = Moderate, 3 = Severe. Statistical analysis performed using Chi-square test. $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant (*), $p < 0.01$ = highly significant (**). NS = Not significant

Table 4 outlines the severity of hoarseness of voice at various postoperative intervals. At 0 hours, more patients in the EMLA group reported no hoarseness (76 vs 36; $\chi^2=14.28$, $p=0.0002^{**}$), while mild hoarseness was significantly higher in the KY Jelly group (60 vs 21; $\chi^2=18.78$, $p=0.0001^{**}$); moderate hoarseness showed no significant difference (13 vs 9; $\chi^2=0.72$, $p=0.40$), and severe cases occurred only in the KY Jelly group (0 vs 5; $\chi^2=5$, $p=0.025^*$). At 2 hours, the EMLA group continued to show advantage, with more patients without hoarseness (97 vs 71; $\chi^2=4.02$, $p=0.04^*$), fewer mild cases (9 vs 27; $\chi^2=9$,

$p=0.002^{**}$), and fewer moderate cases (4 vs 12; $\chi^2=4$, $p=0.045^*$). At 4 hours, no significant difference was noted in patients without hoarseness (107 vs 89; $\chi^2=1.65$, NS), although mild cases remained significantly fewer in the EMLA group (3 vs 21; $\chi^2=13.5$, $p=0.002^*$); no moderate or severe cases were reported. At 6 hours, almost all patients in the EMLA group were symptom-free (109 vs 103; $\chi^2=0.17$, $p=0.68$), with only 1 mild case compared to 7 in the KY Jelly group ($\chi^2=4.5$, $p=0.035^*$). At 12 hours, hoarseness was virtually absent, with 110 patients symptom-free in the EMLA group versus 107 in KY Jelly ($\chi^2=0.04$, $p=0.84$), and only 3 mild cases in the KY group ($\chi^2=3$, $p=0.08$). By 24 hours, both groups showed almost complete recovery, with no significant difference between them (110 vs 109; $\chi^2=0.0004$, $p=0.98$), and just one mild case persisting in the KY Jelly group ($p=0.31$).

Table 5: Number of patients requiring treatment for POST

Time (hrs)	EMLA	KY Jelly	p-value
2 hr	51	93	0.0005**
4 hr	59	98	0.0019**
6 hr	14	56	0.0001**
12 hr	5	18	0.006**
24 hr	3	7	0.2058

Values expressed as number of patients. POST = Postoperative sore throat. Statistical analysis performed using Chi-square test. $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant (*), $p < 0.01$ = highly significant (**).

Table 5 reports the number of patients requiring treatment for POST at different time points. At 2 hours, significantly fewer patients in the EMLA group required treatment compared to KY Jelly (51 vs 93; $p=0.0005^{**}$). This pattern continued at 4 hours (59 vs 98; $p=0.0019^{**}$) and 6 hours (14 vs 56; $p=0.0001^{**}$), as well as at 12 hours (5 vs 18; $p=0.006^{**}$). By 24 hours, treatment needs were minimal in both groups (3 vs 7), with no statistically significant difference ($p=0.2058$).

Discussion: This randomized controlled study demonstrated that 5% EMLA cream applied to the endotracheal tube (ETT) cuff significantly reduced the incidence and severity of postoperative sore throat

(POST), cough, and hoarseness compared to KY Jelly, with the most pronounced effects seen in the first 6–12 hours after extubation. The benefits diminished by 24 hours, consistent with earlier findings suggesting that EMLA's protective effects are predominantly short-term^{15,16,17}

Age distribution between groups (Table 1) and ASA grading (Table 2) were comparable, showing no significant differences, which strengthens the reliability of intergroup comparisons. Similar to Murugaiyan et al. (2023) (15) and Fenta et al. (2020) (18), age and ASA status did not influence outcomes, indicating that baseline characteristics were evenly matched. Duration of surgery (Table 3) was also statistically non-significant between groups, suggesting that observed differences in outcomes were primarily attributable to the intervention rather than surgical length.

Analysis of POST severity (Table 2) revealed that EMLA markedly reduced sore throat at 0, 2, 4, and 6 hours, with significantly more patients remaining symptom-free compared to KY Jelly. Mild and moderate cases were consistently fewer in the EMLA group, and severe POST was virtually absent in both cohorts. These results corroborate Murugaiyan et al. (2023) (15), who observed significantly lower rates of POST with EMLA in the first 6 hours postoperatively.

Cough severity outcomes (Table 3) also favored EMLA, with significantly higher cough-free rates across all early time points. At 0, 2, 4, and 6 hours, mild and moderate cough were consistently lower in the EMLA group, with no severe cough reported. By 12 and 24 hours, differences between groups became statistically insignificant, mirroring trends in POST resolution. These findings align with Murugaiyan et al. (2023) (15), who reported short-term but clinically relevant reductions in cough with EMLA. Similarly, hoarseness of voice (Table 4) was significantly reduced in the EMLA group during the immediate postoperative period. At 0 and 2 hours, significantly more patients were free of hoarseness, and mild-to-moderate cases were lower compared to KY Jelly. By 4–6 hours, hoarseness further decreased, and by 12–24 hours, both groups had near-complete recovery, consistent with previous reports (Larijani et al., 2000 (19); Sohmer et al., 2004 (20)). Murugaiyan et al. (2023) (15) also reported reduced hoarseness in the EMLA cohort during the early postoperative period, supporting our findings. The number of patients requiring treatment for POST (Table 5) further underscores the clinical benefit of EMLA. At 2, 4, 6, and 12 hours, significantly fewer patients in the EMLA group required additional management compared to KY Jelly ($p < 0.01$). By 24 hours, treatment needs had diminished in both groups, with no significant difference, highlighting EMLA's role in early but not long-term symptom control.

Taken together, these findings support EMLA as a safe, effective, and non-invasive strategy for reducing intubation-related airway morbidity. Its effects are most notable in the immediate postoperative period, improving patient comfort and satisfaction. The results are consistent with prior studies evaluating EMLA and other topical anaesthetics in airway management (Vickers et al., 1997 (21); Junputipong

et al., 2022 (16); Martellucci et al., 2014 (17)), and suggest that its application on the ETT cuff may be preferable to KY Jelly, which primarily provides lubrication without anaesthetic properties. In conclusion, application of 5% EMLA cream on the ETT cuff significantly reduced the incidence and severity of POST, cough, and hoarseness in adult female patients undergoing gynaecological surgery compared to KY Jelly, especially in the early postoperative hours. Given its safety profile, ease of use, and short-term efficacy, EMLA represents a valuable adjunct for improving postoperative airway outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the application of 5% EMLA cream on the endotracheal tube cuff significantly reduced the incidence and severity of postoperative sore throat, cough, and hoarseness compared to KY Jelly, particularly within the first 6–12 hours after extubation. The intervention proved safe, simple, and effective, enhancing postoperative comfort and patient satisfaction without increasing adverse effects, thereby establishing EMLA cream as a valuable adjunct in airway management for female patients undergoing gynaecological surgery.

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Authors' Contributions

Dr Vardaan Bhardwaj: Concept, study design, data collection, manuscript drafting.

Dr Vigya Goyal: Data analysis, interpretation, critical revision of manuscript.

Dr Avnish Bharadwaj: Patient management, data collection, literature review.

Dr Vijay Mathur: Supervision, final approval of manuscript.

All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan (Approval No.: [insert number]). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrolment.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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